

Fig S14. Model components extracted from experimental cell track of Fig 7 for two pairs of model weights ($w_{\text{prot}}, w_{\text{APCSF}}, w_{\text{AAF}}$): (6.634, 0.057, 3.532) and (17.190, 0.047, 31.076). The model weights were estimated by minimizing sums of squared residuals: S (left column) and S^+ (right column), see S1 Text for more details. While the first approach enforces small corrections of f_{prot} , positive values of f_{prot} are favored in the second approach. The following kymographs are displayed: Protrusion component (**A, B**), APCSF component (**C, D**), and AAF component (**E, F**), as well as their proportion on the overall velocity of the contour dynamics (**G, H**).